

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Ontogeny of migration destination, route and timing in a partially migratory bird

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Abstract

1. In migratory animals, the developmental period from inexperienced juveniles to breeding adults could be a key life stage in shaping population migration patterns. Nevertheless, the development of migration routines in early life remains under-explored. While age-related changes in migration routes and timing have been described in obligate migrants, most investigations into the ontogeny of partial migrants only focused on age-dependency of migration as a binary tactic (migrant or resident), and variations in routes and timing among individuals classified as 'migrants' is rarely considered.
2. To fill this gap, we study the ontogeny of migration destination, route and timing in a partially migratory red kite (*Milvus milvus*) population. Using an extensive GPS-tracking dataset (292 fledglings and 38 adults, with 1–5 migrations tracked per individual), we studied how nine different migration characteristics changed with age and breeding status in migrant individuals, many of which become resident later in life.
3. Individuals departed later from and arrived earlier at the breeding areas as they aged, resulting in a gradual prolongation of stay in the breeding area by 2 months from the first to the fifth migration. Individuals delayed southward migration in the year prior to territory acquirement, and they further delayed it after occupying a territory. Migration routes became more direct with age. Individuals were highly faithful to their wintering site. Migration distance shortened only slightly with age and was more similar among siblings than among unrelated individuals.
4. The large gradual changes in northward and southward migrations suggest a high degree of plasticity in temporal characteristics during the developmental window. However, the high wintering site fidelity points towards large benefits of site familiarity, prompting spatial migratory plasticity to be expressed through a switch to residency.
5. The contrasting patterns of trajectories of age-related changes between spatial and temporal migration characteristics might reflect different mechanisms underlying the expression of plasticity. Investigating such patterns among species

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along the entire spectrum of migration tactics would enable further understanding of the plastic responses exhibited by migratory species to rapid environmental changes.

KEYWORDS

biologging, differential migration, GPS tracking, immature bird, juvenile, raptors

1 | INTRODUCTION

Migration is one of the main adaptations of animals to seasonal changes in climate and resources (Dingle, 2014; Newton, 2010). This periodic movement between distinct places is enabled by a suite of morphological, sensory and physiologically adaptive traits (Piersma et al., 2005). While the ontogenetic perspective is one of the four key aspects that Tinbergen (1963) raised in the study of animal behaviour, the ontogeny of migration remains understudied. One main hurdle in conducting such studies is the difficulty of following the migration of individuals over several annual cycles; however, this has been overcome by recent advances in remote tracking of individual movements (Kays et al., 2022).

Investigating migration from an ontogenetic perspective is drawing increasing attention, as understanding individual plasticity is fundamental to assess how migratory animals can cope with global environmental change (Gill et al., 2019). While most migratory animals can respond to changing environmental conditions to a certain degree throughout their life (Cooper et al., 2015), adults are often very faithful to their wintering sites and highly repeatable in migration timing (Cresswell, 2014; Franklin et al., 2022; Newton, 2010). Fidelity likely evolved due to benefits from relying on past experience (Winger et al., 2019), but it could also limit adjustment to novel environmental conditions (Merkle et al., 2022). It has been suggested that the 'developmental window' of an individual lacking experience in migration, during which it is highly responsive to environment cues (Vansteelant, Kekkonen, & Byholm, 2017), would be a key life stage for adjustments to novel environmental conditions to occur. This window might be particularly relevant in long-lived animals that do not breed at young ages, including some species of birds, sea turtles and mammals. In such species the development of migration routines in immatures may take several years (Abrahms et al., 2021; Grecian et al., 2022; Scott et al., 2014; Sergio et al., 2014).

Tracking studies can provide valuable insight on this window of development of migratory behaviours. Recent studies that followed migration of immature black kites *Milvus migrans*, Cory's shearwaters *Calonectris borealis* and whooping cranes *Grus americana* over multiple years showed that immatures exhibited extended developmental periods, during which learning and refinement of migration occurred (Abrahms et al., 2021; Campioni et al., 2020; Sergio et al., 2014). Black kites, for example, showed a clear distinction in migration timing and performance between pre-breeding and breeding birds (Sergio et al., 2014), reflecting a tight link between

migratory behaviours and life history events. These insightful studies focused on obligate migrant populations, but a broader understanding of the ontogeny of migration requires studying the whole spectrum of migration tactics.

Partial migration, where some individuals of a population migrate seasonally to nonbreeding areas while others remain resident year-round, is exhibited in a wide variety of taxa (Chapman et al., 2011). In some partial-migrant species the individual's migratory tactic (either a migrant or a resident) is fixed throughout its life (Pulido & Berthold, 2010), yet in many others, particularly in long-lived species, individuals may switch between being migrant and resident ('facultative' partial migrants, Berg et al., 2019; Hegemann et al., 2015; Lea et al., 2018). In such cases, being migrant or resident is considered a state-dependent strategy (Chapman et al., 2011), potentially driven by individual attributes (e.g. sex, size and age) and environmental drivers (e.g. temperature). Studies on ontogeny of partial migrants have largely focused on the effect of age on migration tactic as a binary outcome (migrant vs. resident). In these studies, juveniles often tend to be migrant and adults resident (Able & Belthoff, 1998; Arneklev et al., 2022; Bond et al., 2015; Ketterson & Nolan Jr., 1976), but the opposite has also been found (Eggeman et al., 2016). Meanwhile, age-related variations in routes and migration timing of partial migrants received little attention.

To fill this knowledge gap, we investigated the ontogeny of different aspects of migration (destination, route and timing) in a partial migrant. We study a red kite (*Milvus milvus*) population breeding in western Switzerland that has recently transformed from fully migratory to partially migratory, a phenomenon that is shared with many other migratory species (Bonnet-Lebrun et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2012; Satterfield et al., 2015). Historically, all red kites in Switzerland migrated during winter, but since the 1960s an increasing proportion of birds remained resident year-round (Aebischer & Scherler, 2021; Knaus, 2018). A recent study showed that this phenomenon results from the switching of migratory tactic within individuals: while almost all first-year birds are migratory (Scherler et al., 2020), many individuals shift to residency later in life (Witczak et al., 2024).

We expect that the factors known to affect the ontogeny of migration in obligate migrants, namely learning and refinement and the start of reproduction, are also affecting migration ontogeny in this partially migrating red kite population. Additionally, considerable flexibility in migration routes and timing during ontogeny would be expected for a facultative partial migrant (Newton, 2012). The age-related changes in routes and timing

can follow the same direction as the change in migration tactic (from migrant to resident), either because they are driven by the same factors or causally linked. If that is the case for red kites, where most juveniles are migrants and adults are residents, we could expect a gradual shift of migration destination and timing towards residency, that is a gradual shortening of migration distance and lengthening of duration at the breeding area (Figure S1). Alternatively, red kites can maintain the same migratory distance and timing during ontogeny and then abruptly switch to residency (Figure S1).

Here we focus on age-related changes in migratory route, timing and speed in red kites during the first 5 years of life or until residency. Migration characteristics were extracted from GPS-tracks of multiple migrations per individual. To investigate whether ontogenetic changes in migration behaviour may continue in later years of life not available in our dataset of birds of known age (after the fifth year of migration), we compared migratory behaviours in fifth year birds with those tagged as breeding adults. To confirm that age-related patterns in migration are due to behavioural plasticity and not to disappearance of older birds from the migrant population as they died or became residents, we analysed within-subject patterns. To investigate the potential influence of natal origin on migratory behaviours, we quantified the contribution of the brood of origin to the observed variation in migratory behaviours. Finally, to investigate if reproductive maturity has an effect, we tested whether having a breeding territory affected migration routes and timing.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study population

The red kite is a long-lived European raptor species feeding on small mammals, carcasses and anthropogenic food waste (Aebischer & Scherler, 2021). For the last 40 years, an increasing number of red kites breed in Switzerland, contrary to the stable or declining population trends in much of its core breeding range in Germany, France and Spain (BirdLife International, 2022; EBCC, 2022; Keller et al., 2020). In Switzerland, red kites breed in most of the lower-altitude areas and are expanding towards the Alps. Migrating Swiss red kites overwinter in France, Spain, and Portugal; however, more and more red kites are overwintering in Switzerland, as shown in winter roost counts, which increased from ca. 1400 individuals in 2008/2009 to over 4000 in 2020 (Aebischer & Scherler, 2021; Knaus, 2018; Schmid & Volet, 2004). Almost all juveniles (>95%) are migratory (Scherler et al., 2020). In this study population, a small percentage of individuals already switched from migrant to resident in the second calendar year, and the probability of switching to resident increased with age (Witczak et al., 2024). Our study area of about 390 km² with an altitude of 450–1600 m is located on the border of the cantons of Freiburg and Bern in Switzerland (46.78°N, 7.25°E). Breeding density was high within this area, with 30 breeding pairs

per 100 km² (Knaus, 2018) producing 1.77 ± 0.7 fledglings per brood (from 2015 to 2018, Nägeli et al., 2022).

2.2 | GPS logger deployment

We deployed GPS loggers on 391 fledglings from 2015 to 2020 and 76 adults (at least 4 years old, but likely older due to high survival and long lifespan of this species, Witczak et al., 2024) from 2016 to 2018 (number of individuals tagged per year is presented in Table S1). All deployments were conducted during the breeding season. Nestlings of about 35–45 days old, just before fledging, were caught on the nest by a tree climber (Nägeli et al., 2022). Adults were caught using a Dho-Gaza net during mobbing events elicited by a live decoy of their natural predator, Eurasian eagle owl *Bubo bubo*, once their nestlings were >10 days old (Witczak et al., 2024). Tagged birds were ringed, measured and a blood sample was taken to genetically determine sex (see Nägeli et al., 2022 for details). We attached 25–26 g solar-powered GPS-GSM-UHF loggers (SKUA/CREX, Ecotone Telemetry, Gdynia, Poland, or GsmRadioTag-M9, Milsar, Cluj Napoca, Romania) onto the bird using a body harness. Loggers weighed about 2.5% of the adult body mass. GPS locations were logged at an interval of 1 h during daytime and were transmitted via GSM, 2G or 3G networks. The tracking data were accessed and managed through Movebank (Kays et al., 2022). Ringing and tagging of red kites was done under Permit No. 2015_13_FR and 2017_29_FR issued by the Canton of Fribourg Amt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen and the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment.

2.3 | Extracting migration characteristics from tracking data

Data processing and statistical analyses were performed using the R software, version 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2023). For each non-breeding season, we first classified an individual as migrant or resident. A migrant is defined by having moved south and crossed 46°N. The latitude cut-off of 46°N (referred to as 'breeding latitude' hereafter) was selected as it lies at geographical boundaries (the southern edge of Lake of Geneva and Jura mountains) between our study area and habitats further south.

For the migrants, we then characterised their migration journeys with a suite of spatial (migration distance, fidelity of wintering site, migration route directness and fidelity) and temporal characteristics (departure and arrival time at breeding latitude, i.e. our study area, departure and arrival time at wintering area and speed). We first determined the period away from the breeding latitude for each individual. Specifically, departure from the breeding area was defined as the date of the first GPS point at a latitude <46°N within a track segment with movement directed towards the non-breeding areas in southwestern Europe. Arrival to the breeding area corresponded to the date of the first location

after crossing latitude 46°N when returning to the breeding area from the non-breeding area.

The wintering site was defined as the location where the individual stayed longest during the entire period away from the breeding area. For each individual, during the period away from the breeding area, we subsampled one location per half-day (to reduce computational time) and for each location, we calculated 'residence time' (Barraquand & Benhamou, 2008) within a radius of 10 km using the 'recurse' package in R (Bracis et al., 2018). The wintering site was defined as the location with the longest residence time. Migration distance was defined as the great circle (direct) distance between wintering site and the nest site. For individuals tagged as juveniles, the nest site was where it was born. For breeding adults, that was the nest location, and in the case of non-breeding adults, the centre of their territory in the breeding season. For those individuals without information of their territory, we took the centre of locations within 30 days before departing from the breeding area. Adult nest and territory locations were verified by field observations. Fidelity of the wintering site was partly reflected in the repeatability of migration distance, although this metric would not capture the shift between wintering sites of similar distances to the breeding site. Therefore, we further quantified it using the distance between wintering sites in two consecutive years.

To quantify the directness of the northward/southward migration route, we calculated the shortest absolute distance between the actual migration route and each of 100 evenly distributed points along the direct (great circle) path between the wintering and breeding site (Brown et al., 2021). The mean of the distances represented the indirectness of the route, with smaller mean values representing a more direct path. Fidelity of the migration route was calculated in the same way, comparing the current year's migration route with the previous year's route of the same individual. Smaller mean values of the distances, thus, represented closer proximity of the current year's route to that of the previous year.

Arrival time at the wintering area was defined as the moment when an individual reached the latitude of its wintering site, thus including any short stops south of its wintering site. Departure from the wintering area was the moment the individual crossed the wintering site's latitude during northward migration. Southward migration duration was the time between departure from the breeding area (defined above) and arrival at the wintering site, and northward migration duration was the time elapsed between departure from the wintering site and arrival at the breeding area. Migration speed was the total distance of the route travelled divided by the migration duration.

Reproductive status was defined by territory establishment and was determined as follows: first, using the GPS trajectory, we extracted 95% maximum convex polygon (MCP) in 10-day time windows during the breeding season (February–July). If the 95% MCP was smaller than 30 km² in two consecutive weeks, we conducted field observations to confirm territorial behaviour (e.g. defending of a forest patch, courtship behaviour, calling from a potential breeding site, copulation, nest building, feeding of a mate). For the confirmed

territories, we defined territory boundaries based on the 95% MCP for the entire breeding period.

2.4 | Statistical analysis

We used linear mixed effect models to test for the effects of age, sex and their interaction on the nine migratory characteristics described above, applied to the dataset of birds that were tagged as fledglings ('juvenile dataset'), containing location data collected from June 2015 to June 2021. Models were fitted in a Bayesian framework (R package 'rstanarm') (Goodrich et al., 2020). We used the default priors automatically generated and checked for any influence of the priors by calculating prior-posterior overlap (see Appendix 1 for details). Four of the migration characteristics (distance between wintering sites of consecutive years, mean distance to direct route, mean distance to route of previous year and migration speed) were log-transformed so that the residuals became normally distributed. The remaining migration characteristics were analysed as Gaussian response variables on the observed scale. Following Sergio et al. (2014), a bird was classified as age 1 from birth to 30 June of the next year, and then it became age 2 and so on. Therefore, the first year of life ('age 1') contains the first southward migration and the first northward migration. Our analysis used tracks from age 1–5. Sex was included as an explanatory variable as migration distances were found to differ between sexes in the Czech and Slovakian red kite population (Literák et al., 2022), and males might be exposed to stronger pressure for early arrival at the breeding area to acquire a breeding territory ('Arrival time hypothesis', Ketterson & Nolan Jr., 1976). Season (autumn southward vs. spring northward migration) was included as a fixed factor in the analyses of migration route and speed. To account for individuals being tracked for multiple years, we included individual identity as a random intercept. To investigate whether birds from the same nest in the same year (siblings) were more similar in migratory behaviours than birds from different nests, we included brood identity as a random effect; individuals were nested in broods. To control for interannual effects, we also included year as a random intercept. For the models concerning route, we controlled for migration distance by including it as an explanatory variable since migrating further would mean a higher chance of deviating from the direct path (directness) and previous year's path (fidelity). For models on timing, we also controlled for migration distance. All continuous explanatory variables were scaled and centred. For birds tagged as adults, we fitted the same linear mixed models without age and brood identity, as they were unavailable or irrelevant for the adult dataset.

We calculated 95% credible intervals (CrI) for the estimates from the posterior draws. For each model, we plotted age against the residuals to check whether age would be best modelled as a linear effect, quadratic effect or a factor (see Appendix 1 for details). For northward departure and arrival dates, when age was modelled as a linear effect, we observed a poor fit from the residual plot. Therefore, we modelled

age as a quadratic effect using an orthogonal polynomial. For all other parameters, age was modelled as a linear effect.

Two food supplementation experiments were conducted within our study population during the study period primarily for other purposes. In 2015–2018, food (dead farmed day-old chickens) was supplemented to a subset of nests during the period from hatching till fledging (Nägeli et al., 2022; Scherler et al., 2023). In 2017–2019, from August to February, another experiment targeting adults was conducted. To check for potential effects of the food supplementation, we plotted residuals of the models against treatment, and we found no effects. We also plotted model residuals against hatching date and tarsus length (a proxy of size) and did not find any support for effects of these parameters.

To tease apart the effect of between-individual and within-individual variation underlying the age effect, we fitted the models described above with within-subject centring, that is subtracting each individual's mean value from each observation value, with individuals with ≥ 3 migrations tracked in the juvenile dataset (van de Pol & Wright, 2009; see Appendix 1 for more information).

To compare the contributions of bird identities, brood identities and year in explaining observed variation, we conducted a variance component analysis. This analysis partitions the variance unexplained by the fixed effects among the random terms. Variance components were calculated from the posterior draws from the same model that was used above with fixed effects of age, sex and so forth. From each draw we calculated the percentage of variance explained by bird identities, brood identities and year; then we extracted the median and 95% quantiles of these percentages.

To investigate how reproductive status affects migration ontogeny, we focused on the first breeding attempt, which we defined as the age an individual acquired their first breeding territory. The average age of first territory acquisition was 4.0 ± 0.7 (range 3–5), and territorial individuals remained territorial in the years after. We classified reproductive status as '1st territory' for the southward and northward migrations occurring just before they acquired their first territory. Migrations occurring in the years before '1st territory' were assigned as 'no territory'. Migrations occurring after '1st territory' were assigned the reproductive status '2nd+ territory'. We fitted an additional set of models, in which reproductive status was added as a factor into the model described above for the juvenile dataset (a subset of age 2–5 individuals were used since red kites only acquire a territory from age 3 onwards).

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Effect of age on migration characteristics

Most tagged red kites (97%) were migratory in their first year, but the proportion of migratory individuals decreased with age. Among the 70 birds tracked since adulthood (exact age unknown), 36 were migratory for at least 1 year (for more details, see Appendix 1). For the migrants, wintering destinations spread over a wide range of latitudes

(36.9–45.4°N), scattered from the southern Iberian Peninsula to southern France (Figure 1). Birds of age 1 migrated, on average, to wintering sites 873 km away (SD=294 km), and migration distance decreased very slightly with age by 28 km/year (95% CrI: 1–52 km/year, Table S2, Figure 2). Wintering site fidelity did not change with age (Table S2, Figure 2). As birds aged, migration route became more direct and more similar to the previous year's route (Table S2, Figure 2). Sex differences in migration distance in younger birds disappeared by adulthood (Table S2, Figure 1). Northward migration was generally more direct than southward migration (Table S2, Figure 2).

Birds left the breeding area, on average, on 16 October (SD=28 days, range: 28 June–24 January) and returned 19 March (SD=32 days, 23 December–10 August, Figure 3). As an individual became 1 year older, it departed in autumn from the breeding area 13.6 days (95% CrI: 10.6–16.3 days) later and arrived at the wintering area 9.9 days (6.1–13.6) later. Across ages, males departed from the breeding area 5.6 days (1.2–9.9) later than females; however, this delay disappeared by the time they arrived at the wintering area (Table S2, Figure 3). In spring, older birds arrived earlier at the breeding area, but the degree of advancement in time diminished with age, as shown in the statistically supported quadratic age effect (Table S2, Figure 3). Sex differences in northward migration timing disappeared by adulthood (Table S2). Lastly, migration speed did not change with age, but it was faster in northward than in southward migration (Table S2).

For all migration characteristics showing an age effect (Table S2), the slope of within-individual age effects in the within-subject centring analysis had credible intervals that did not overlap zero (Table S3). This demonstrated that age-dependent changes indeed occurred within individuals.

3.2 | Brood and individual differences in migratory behaviour

Among-brood differences were found to be unimportant in migration characteristics, except for migration distance, where brood identity explained 26.1% of the variance (Figure 4, Table S4). Among-individual differences in behaviour were found in both the juvenile and adult datasets (Table S4). In the juvenile dataset, bird identity explained 49.4% of the variance in migration distance and 16%–39% of the variance in departure/arrival timing between the wintering and breeding areas (Figure 4, Table S4). Bird identity also explained 27.7% of the variance in route directness. In the adult dataset, for most migration characteristics, bird identity explained more of the variance than it did in the juvenile dataset (Table S4).

3.3 | Effect of reproductive status

Reproductive status affected the timing of southward migration but not the migration route. Birds delayed departure from the breeding latitude by 8.7 days (2.9–14.6) the year before they occupied their

FIGURE 1 Migration tracks and wintering sites of (a) age 1 and (b) adult (age 4 or above) red kites, with pink dots indicating females and blue dots for males. Five years of tracking data of a (c) male and a (d) female red kite tagged in Switzerland at fledging. Winter 2016 refers to July 2016–June 2017, and so on. Map of a wider area in Europe (bottom left) with rectangles indicating the areas plotted.

first breeding territory, compared to birds of the same age that did not have a territory the following year (Table S5). They further delayed departure by 24.4 days (15.4–33.4) after they had a territory (Table S5). Arrival at the wintering site followed the same delay, with 9.3 days (2.6–15.8) prior to establishing their first territory, and 29.9 days (20.0–39.8) in the years after (Table S5). Migration speed of birds with a territory was slower than that of their counterparts of the same age without a territory. No effect of breeding territory was found on the remaining migration characteristics.

4 | DISCUSSION

Our study investigated the ontogenetic development of both spatial and temporal aspects of migratory behaviour in a partially migratory population of red kites, where most juveniles are migratory and switch

to residency later in life. Migration distance changed little with age, as the majority of migrants were faithful to their wintering sites; consequently, the switch to residency at age 2 onwards (Witczak et al., 2024) seem abrupt (Appendix 1, Figure A3). On the contrary, migration timing changed substantially with age, with later departures from the breeding area in autumn and earlier departures from the wintering area in spring, resulting in a 2-month prolongation of the time spent in the breeding area from age 1 to age 5. Therefore, migration timing changed gradually towards residency. As birds grew older, they migrated along a more direct route and were more faithful to their route.

4.1 | Ontogeny of migration timing

We showed large shifts in the timing of migration with age in migratory red kites, both in terms of an advancement of northward

FIGURE 2 How migration distance, distance to direct route and distance to previous route vary with age in migratory red kites tagged in Switzerland. Predictions (hollow circles) with 95% credible intervals are based on linear mixed models (see [Table S2](#) for model estimates). Small dots in the background indicate raw data points. Only differences with 95% credible intervals not overlapping zero between sexes and seasons (autumn southward/spring northward) are presented.

FIGURE 3 Age-dependent change of migration timing in red kites tagged in Switzerland. Predictions (circles/triangles) with 95% credible intervals are based on linear mixed models (see [Table S2](#) for model estimates). Small dots in the background indicate raw data points. Only sex differences with credible intervals not overlapping zero are presented; hence, for southward departure from the breeding area, the overall age-effect is shown.

migration and a delay in southward migration. The advancement of northward migration followed the patterns of many migratory species, which is explained by the increase in reproductive potential with age (Campioni et al., 2020; McKinnon et al., 2014). Moreover, the earlier return of age 1 males than females is in line with the idea that males, being the sex acquiring territories, benefit more from returning early to the breeding area (Bejarano & Jahn, 2018; Sirot & Touzalin, 2014). However, we did not see any effect of breeding

territory establishment on northward migration timing. Interestingly, the advancement in arriving at the breeding area was not driven by increasing migrating speed, as speed did not change with age, contrary to patterns in speed improvement found in long-distance migrating raptors such as the black kite (Sergio et al., 2014). Instead, the advancement in arrival timing is driven by similar advancement in departure timing from wintering area, and the straightening of routes could also contribute to the shortening migration duration.

FIGURE 4 Variance components of migration characteristics explained by individual (yellow) and brood (blue) identities (random effects) in tagged red kites (age 1–5). Grey line indicates 95% credible intervals.

The considerable delay in autumn departure from the breeding area with age (10 days per year) in red kites does not follow the pattern of previous studies tracking migratory birds. In most species, juveniles depart from the breeding area at the same time or later than adults (Gschweng et al., 2008; Hake et al., 2003; Sergio et al., 2014; Vansteelant, Kekkonen, & Byholm, 2017; Verhoeven et al., 2022). However, our result is in line with an observational study showing that adults migrated later than juveniles in 8 of 10 raptor species (Mueller et al., 2000), which were all short-distance, intra-continental migrants. As previous studies showing adults migrate earlier than juveniles were mostly on long-distance, inter-continental migrants, how age-related differential migration timing differ between inter- and intra-continental migrants warrants further investigation.

One potential mechanism underlying the gradual delay of departing to the wintering area is that the onset of southward migration is modulated by food availability, as food has been shown experimentally to activate and deactivate migratory restlessness (Fusani et al., 2011; Gwinner et al., 1988). Competitiveness and knowledge on food resources in the breeding area should increase with age, and with better access to food, their migratory restlessness (Stoltz, 2005) could be triggered later in the season as they aged. In addition, red kite juveniles might rely more on social information during migration, while adults could rely on previous knowledge on their route and make it possible to depart later (Brønnvik et al., 2024). The delays in southward migration relating to occupying a breeding territory are in line with the idea that a longer stay in the breeding area in autumn would facilitate defending and pre-occupying breeding territories of high quality (Forstmeier, 2002). At the same time, the longer stay would allow gathering information on winter food resources, which could be useful for staying in the breeding area in winter (i.e. become a resident) later in life. Additionally, migration patterns might also differ between birds that switch from migrant to resident at different ages, but we lack the sample size to investigate this question

since many of our tracked red kites were still migrating at the end of data collection. Only by tracking them for more years can we compare migration patterns between individuals that switch to residency at different ages and those that remain migratory for the rest of their lives.

4.2 | Ontogeny of migration routes

Tracked red kites migrated along a more direct route and were more faithful to their route as they grew older. The more direct route and increased route fidelity might reflect that first-year birds were collecting personal information or social information while migrating, and as they grew older, they increasingly rely on their previous knowledge during migration. This aligns with findings on white stork that individuals used less social information and more personal information as they grew older (Brønnvik et al., 2024). In addition, more direct route and route fidelity could also result from improvement in the ability to take advantage of favourable environmental conditions or deal with unfavourable ones, especially regarding wind (Sergio et al., 2022; Thorup et al., 2003). Moreover, the deviation from the direct route (around 10–30 km) was small compared to the hundreds of kilometres of detours found in long-distance migrants. This is probably because the migratory routes of red kites are along suitable habitats; in contrast, long distance migrants are more likely to use detours for example to avoid unfavourable habitats (Hahn et al., 2014), or take advantage of better wind conditions (Vansteelant, Shamoun-Baranes, et al., 2017).

We showed that the distance between the breeding and wintering sites of migratory individuals decreased only slightly with age. Most individuals did not transition from being migrant to resident by gradually wintering at sites closer to the breeding area (Appendix 1, Figure A3). Fidelity to wintering sites is commonly found in migratory

species across a broad range of taxa (Broderick et al., 2007; Horton et al., 2017; Newton, 2010), although most studies were on adults, and juveniles are thought to be more flexible. In our case, most individuals already exhibited fidelity to wintering sites since age 1, which suggests high benefits of familiarity with local resources at the wintering site selected in the first winter. Overall, these results suggest that the migration destination in the first year largely determines the destination and routes in subsequent years.

The findings on the pivotal role of the first-year migration destination in shaping migration behaviours in the years that follow encourage further exploration on what determines the first migration destination. We found that brood identity explains a moderate amount of variation in migration distance, suggesting that genetics, epigenetics (e.g. maternal effects) or environmental factors at the nest play a role. Our data do not allow pinpointing the exact mechanism, but the absence of an effect of the nest feeding experiment suggests that differences between brood in migration distance were not due to differences in food availability or the associated variation in body condition (Catitti et al., 2022; Nägeli et al., 2022). Past studies showed that long-distance migrants generally express longer periods of migratory restlessness than short-distance migrants and that the period of migratory restlessness has a heritable component. This suggests that the first migration distance might be partly heritable (Berthold & Querner, 1981; Bulte & Bairlein, 2013; Maggini & Bairlein, 2010). On the other hand, wind conditions *en route* explained a substantial part of variation in the route of the first migration of a long-distance migrating raptor, the honey buzzard *Pernis apivorus*, suggesting that stochastic environmental processes could also play a major role (Vansteelant, Kekkonen, & Byholm, 2017). While our data do not allow inference of genetic effects, future studies on the first migration of parent-offspring pairs, individuals with a pedigree or cross-fostering experiments could clarify the contributions of genetic and stochastic environmental processes in determining the first migration destination.

4.3 | Ontogeny of migration and adaptations in a changing world

To generalise patterns in the ontogeny of migration beyond individual species, it would be necessary to establish links between ontogenetic patterns and ecological and life-history traits. Longevity has been proposed as one driver of these patterns, and our results support the idea that species with longer lifespans tend to have extended developmental windows. Our results also shed light on possible ontogenetic patterns of migration in other partial migratory species which recently reduced their tendency to migrate (Bonnet-Lebrun et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2012; Satterfield et al., 2015). Moreover, red kites are generalists and the area between their breeding and wintering areas are hospitable year-round. Under such circumstances, all sorts of changes in migration patterns are not constrained by the environment, and the patterns revealed by this study should reflect the least costly pathways. While red kites

showed substantial gradual changes in migration timing with age, they also showed high fidelity to their wintering site. This is contrary to the expectation of low site fidelity in facultative partial migrants (Newton, 2012), and suggests that site fidelity (presumably evolved due to benefits of familiarity, Winger et al., 2019) confers high benefits. The switch to residency can also be interpreted as a spatial response that preserves site familiarity, as red kites can 're-use' their knowledge on their breeding site. Our results also hints that the potential constraint of site fidelity on adaptations to human-induced environmental changes (Merkle et al., 2022) might be more relevant to short-distance and partial migrants than previously thought.

Anthropogenic activities have led to rapid changes in the spatial and temporal distributions of resources on which many migratory animals rely (Aikens et al., 2020; Middleton et al., 2013), and changes in routes, timing and propensity of migration have been regarded as responses to such environmental changes (Bonnet-Lebrun et al., 2020; Conklin et al., 2021; Lawrence et al., 2022; Nuijten et al., 2020; Teitelbaum et al., 2016; Tillotson et al., 2021). A key question is whether substantial adjustments to environmental change can be accomplished through behavioural plasticity (Beever et al., 2017; Conklin et al., 2021; Gienapp et al., 2007). This is believed to depend on how 'hard-wired' a species' migratory behaviour is: migratory patterns are thought to vary along a spectrum from 'hard-wired' (i.e. predominantly endogenous control) to 'soft-wired' (predominantly external control), with the former being a characteristic of long-distance, obligate migrants, and the latter in short-distance, partial migrants (Hurlbert & Liang, 2012; La Sorte et al., 2016; Newton, 2012). The ontogenetic perspective that we exemplify in this study adds yet another dimension to this spectrum. Young individuals developing their migration routines are assumed to be more responsive to the surrounding environment than adults (Senner et al., 2015). Therefore, the knowledge of how plasticity in different spatial and temporal characteristics changes across ontogenetic stages is crucial to have a complete picture of how and when adaptations could occur. On a related note, how 'hard-wired' a species is could also be under selection and change through time: one could contemplate whether selection for flexibility (West-Eberhard, 2003) might have occurred in obligate migratory populations that recently became partially migratory. To progress towards a better understanding of the mechanisms by which adaptation to rapid global environmental changes can occur, we encourage further investment in tracking migratory species and populations of diverse ecological requirements and life-history strategies from their first migration onwards.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Ying-Chi Chan: Conceptualisation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing. Urs G. Kormann: Project administration, resources, supervision, writing—review and editing. Stephanie Witczak: Data curation, investigation, methodology, writing—review and editing. Patrick Scherler: Data curation, project administration, resources, writing—review and editing. Martin U. Grüebler: Conceptualisation,

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

We declare that we have no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data available from the Zenodo Repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12093710> (Chan et al., 2024).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Appendix 1. Additional details on methods and results.

Table A1. Mean and standard deviation of the prior distributions used, and the prior-posterior overlap for fixed predictors of the models investigating effects of age and sex on nine migration characteristics in red kites tagged in Switzerland (estimates of these models are presented in Table S2).

Figure A1. Predictions from models where age was modelled as linear or quadratic effect (black) or as independent factor levels (gray).

Figure A2. Proportion of migrants and residents across age and sex in individual red kites tagged since fledging.

Figure A3. Individual change in migration distance with age of GPS-tagged red kites ($n = 52$) known to switch from migrant to resident.

Figure S1. Schematic diagram depicting two possible scenarios of how migration destination and time spent in the breeding area within the annual cycle can change with age in a partial migrant, before it switches from migrant to resident: a gradual shift in migration destination and lengthening of the time spent in the breeding area vs. migration destination and time spent in the breeding area remaining the same across ages.

Table S1. Number of red kite adults and fledglings tagged by year at western Switzerland in this study, included those that were later excluded in the analysis, i.e. those with unknown sex, those that died or its tag failed before we can determine if the individual is a migrant or a resident.

Table S2. Estimates of the linear mixed models investigating effects of age and sex on nine migration characteristics in red kites tagged in Switzerland, controlling for migration distance (fixed effect) and bird identity, brood identity and year (random effects).

Table S3. Estimates and 95 % Credible intervals from the within-subject centering analysis of the effect of age on migration characteristics of red kites with ≥ 3 years of tracking data from 2015 to 2021, applying equation 2 in van de Pol and Wright (2009).

Table S4. Variance components of bird and brood identities from the linear mixed models investigating effects of age, sex and season on nine migration characteristics in red kites tagged in Switzerland (estimates of fixed effects are presented in Table S2).

Table S5. Estimates of the linear mixed models investigating effects of age, sex, season and breeding territory on nine migration characteristics in red kites tagged in Switzerland, controlling for migration distance (fixed effect) as well as bird identity, brood identity, and year (random effects).

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